

*Latin Aqua is from a root-word that referred to the Sea that encloses and surrounds, the Sea which girds like a girdle/belt/a serpent; with Aqua cognate with Aquila=eagle; the meaning “eagle” in my view developing from the earlier meaning “(the) gripper”, from the way raptors grab prey; the older meaning of Aqua is seen more easily in Old Norse Ægir, the North Sea; and Ægir since long ago has been proposed to be cognate to Latin Aqua; and likewise I posit that PIE *h₂ep- “water; body of water” derives from the homonymous PIE *h₂ep- “to join, attach, fasten, fit; to grab, snatch, get”*

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A few weeks ago I was reading a new paper by the linguist Douglas G. Kilday, wherein he proposes that the *-inque-* and *-inqu(i)e-* portions found in the Latin words *co(n)inquere* and *coinqu(i)endi* are cognate to Latin *aqua*, via a nasal infix (translation of “nasal infix”: the “N” sound was added to the root: so picture “anqua” instead of “aqua”; then shift the vowel from A to I: and we get “inqua”) a good idea, in my opinion, as we shall see; but I disagree with his theory that *aqua* comes from the semantic origin that he posits in his paper.

In his theory, *aqua* is from an old collective noun with a retracted accent, a noun which had the meaning “depths”, in turn from a hypothetical resultive-terminative *h₁eh₁k^w- “send to the depths, send to the bottom”, in turn from a hypothetical *h₁ek^w- “send down, place down”. Here, by “hypothetical”, I mean that Kilday himself originated those hypotheses.

My conclusion on the other hand is that Latin *aqua* comes from an older meaning of “engirdle”, referring to the sea that engirdles the land, the great sea which among most ancient peoples was believed to completely

encircle the land upon earth. The Old Norse *Ægir* indeed referred to the sea, as well as to a mythical being who was the personification of the sea.

One of the many things that point to my theory are the meanings of the Latin words *co(n)inquere* and *coinqu(i)endi* : *coinquere* was glossed by Paulus Diaconus as meaning “*coercere*”, while the same Paulus Diaconus glossed *coninquere* as meaning “*deputare*”. The Latin word *coercere* is from *coerceō*, which means:

- 1.to [enclose](#) on all sides, [hold](#) together; [surround](#), [encompass](#)
- 2.to [restrain](#), [keep back](#), [confine](#), [shut up](#) or in, hold in [confinement](#), [repress](#)
- 3.(*figuratively, of discourse*) to keep within limits, [control](#), [limit](#)
- 4.(*figuratively, of a passion*) to [curb](#), restrain

Likewise, the reason that Paulus Diaconus stated that *coninquere* means *deputare* is because one of the meanings of *deputare* was “to trim”, as in trimming trees and hedges, bushes and shrubbery, and so here *deputare* is to be understood as a synonym for “to hold back, restrain”, as in to trim a tree or hedge or bush so as to restrain it from growing out and spreading wildly.

On *coinqu(i)endi* having the same meaning as *coercere/coerceō*, I direct the reader to Douglas G. Kilday’s paper titled “*Latin inquam, coinquere, and propinquus*”. Note that there are no other meanings glossed by the ancients for these words beyond what I have stated above; an additional synonym I have seen glossed is *compescere/compescō*, which has the same meanings as *coercere/coerceō* . And note that Kilday does not claim that these Latin words *co(n)inquere* and *coinqu(i)endi* meant anything other than what I describe here: but he argues that the meanings in Latin for *co(n)inquere* and *coinqu(i)endi* derive from an older unattested meaning “to put down”, as in to put down shrubbery that has risen/grown out.

So then, if the *-inque-* and *-inqu(i)e-* portions of *co(n)inquere* and *coinqu(i)endi* are nasal infixed forms of the same word that led to *aqua*, as Kilday proposes; then my theory explains how *co(n)inquere* and *coinqu(i)endi* are semantically related to *aqua*, in a manner that is much more straightforward (“to hold back, to restrain” for *co(n)inquere* and *coinqu(i)endi* and “to hold, grasp, restrain, engirdle” for the aquatic word,

referring to how the sea holds back and restrains the land, similar to restraining vegetation from growing out wild in all directions) and in my opinion much more likely than Kilday’s semantic theory regarding their relation: I recommend that the reader read Kilday’s draft paper, “*Latin inquam, coinquere, and propinquus*”, in conjunction with my paper, because in this draft version I am speeding to publish, and I do not currently have time to detail Kilday’s theory, which he details in his draft paper.

My theory is also indicated by the fact that in the Indo-European linguistic literature, we find PIE $*h_2ep-$, “water, body of water” as well as a PIE $*h_2ep-$, “to join, attach, fasten, fit; to grab, snatch, get” (see for example the LIV, page 269). I derive the meanings “water, body of water” from “to engirdle, to grab, to hold, to join, to hold fast” referring to the encircling sea.

The root $*h_2ep-$, “to join, attach, fasten, fit; to grab, snatch, get” is alternatively reconstructed by another linguistic source as $*h_1ep-$, “to join, attach, fasten, fit; to grab, snatch, get”, and linked to PIE $*h_1epi$ “on, at, near”: I agree that $*h_1epi$ derives from the aforementioned $*h_1ep/*h_2ep-$, “to join, attach, fasten, fit; to grab, snatch, get”, and I expect that the meanings “to grab, to grasp” led to “join together”, which led to “on, at; to bring close”; and “to bring close” led to “near”. I expect that the root $*h_2ep-$, “to join, attach, fasten, fit; to grab, snatch, get” existed in both h1 and h2 laryngeal variants: $*h_1ep/*h_2ep-$.

The PIE root $*h_2ep-$ “water, body of water” has been alternatively reconstructed as $*h_2eb-$ and $*h_2eb^h-$, with the same meanings; if either of those reconstructions are correct, I still expect that $*h_1ep/*h_2ep-$, “to join, attach, fasten, fit; to grab, snatch, get” would be the source of a $*h_2eb-$ or $*h_2eb^h-$ root meaning “water, body of water”, either via a sound-shift or because $*h_1ep/*h_2ep-$, “to join, attach, fasten, fit; to grab, snatch, get” would have had a Pre-Pie variant $*h_2eb-/*h_2eb^h-$ “to join, attach, fasten, fit; to grab, snatch, get”.

I posit that PIE **h₂ébōl¹* (which meant “apple”) is akin to **h₂ep-/*h₂eb- *h₂eb^h-*, “water, body of water”, but not because apples are rather juicy (but not nearly as juicy as pears, watermelons, and some other fruits; so I don’t think the apple was viewed as a “water (melon)”) but instead because apples are as rounded as they are, sometimes very round, and so often apples are identified with the sun due to their shape, coloration (excluding green apples), vivacity, etc.

And I believe this is a big reason why a mystical apple tree with fruits of immortality was so often located at the edge/circumference of the earth, or on an island that was situated in the great Ocean stream/river that was believed to encircle the earth: I expect that the very etymology of **h₂ébōl* linked the round apple with the round circumference of the “flat” earth, where the circular ocean stream began.

So I’m positing a semantic spectrum here that included “to engirdle/to encircle” and “circle” and “circumference” and “round”, if not also “to curve, bend”: and “to curve, bend” could have been the source of the meanings “to engirdle”, “to bend around”, “to enclose”, “to grasp around”>”to grasp, to hold, to keep”; and “to bend” leading also to hooked things, like eagle talons and eagle beaks.

My theory posits that the Latin word *aquila* (“eagle”) comes from the earlier meaning “gripper, holder” and/or “the hooked one”, from a root **h₁ek^w-/*h₂ek^w-* which meant “to grip, to grab, to restrain, to keep, to enclose”, likely from “to bend, to curve”, and the reference likely included the curved talons and curved beak, not just the gripping and grabbing of the taloned-toes.

The Latin word *aquilus* (“dark-colored, swarthy”) I believe derives from a semantic shift where “closed” shifted to “dark”, as we see in Romanian where the adjective *închis* means “closed, shut, unopened” but also means “dark, cloudy; sullen”; and the Romanian verb “*a închide*” means

¹ This root is alternatively reconstructed as **h₂ébl* by another source, and as **h₂eph₃ol-* by Matasović, Ranko. *Etymological Dictionary of Proto-Celtic* (Leiden Indo-European Etymological Dictionary Series; 9), Leiden: Brill, page 23.

„to close, to lock” and also „to darken”, among some other meanings which do not concern this paper. The adjective *închis* is from the verb *închide* (the „ch” în Romanian indicates the K sound, aş it does în Italian) which is inherited from Latin *inclūdō*, which meant „to close; enclose; shut up or în, confine, imprison, keep în, restrain, limit; to include something în, incorporate”.

Latin *inclūdō* bears the prefix *in-* attached onto *clūdō*, which is a form of Latin *claudō*; Latin *claudō* derives from PIE **kleh₂w-* “hook, crook, peg”, alternatively reconstructed as **kleh₁w-*, **klew*, **klewH*, **(s)kleh₁w-*, **(s)kleh₂w*.

So at this time I do not agree with nor accept Pokorny’s mid-20th century theory (though his theory is of course still possible at this point in our state of knowledge, and it’s still a good and very plausible theory) that the adjective *aquilus* derives from *aqua*, which would be due to the dark surface appearance of many larger bodies of water (and the dark depths of larger bodies of water); and I recall that Pokorny---or if not Pokorny, another linguist---derives Latin *aquila* (“eagle”) from the fact that eagle plumage is largely made up of dark brown feathers.

Nor do I agree with Cohen 2004: 32, where he derives the adjective *aquilus* from *aquila*, because of the largely dark plumage of eagles.

My theory posits that *aquila* (eagle) derives from “to grip, to enclose, to restrain” referring to the way raptor birds grab/snatch/grip their prey, with long taloned-toes that curve around like hooks: indeed, the meanings “to grip, to enclose, to restrain” likely developed from “to bend” or instead from “firm, tight, strong” or another origin. Here one can note how similar Latin *aquila* is to Latin *anguilla*, which means “eel”.

Anguilla has been posited in the literature to be from a PIE **h₂eng^{wh-}*, “water-worm, eel”, itself akin to or deriving from a PIE **h₂éng^{whis}* “snake”. Cognate with Old Prussian *angurgis* (“eel”), Lithuanian *ungurỹs* (“eel”); Proto-Slavic **qgořb* “eel”; Albanian *ngjalë* (“eel”), if the Albanian word is not a borrowing from Latin as some posit; the Albanian word has the variant

form *njalë*; Ancient Greek ἔγχελῦς (“eel”); Old High German *angar* (“mealworm, grub, larva”).

From PIE **h₂éng^{whis}* derive Latin *anguis* (“snake, serpent”), Old Prussian *angis* (“snake, serpent”), Lithuanian *angìs* (“a viper”), Proto-Slavic **qǫžь* (“snake, serpent”), Latvian *odze* (“viper; adder” and “a bad/evil person”), Old High German *unc* (“snake, serpent; toad”), Old Armenian *oð* (*ōj*) (“snake, serpent”), alternative form *ωιδ* (*awj*).

There is also a PIE root that Beekes reconstructs as **h₃ég^{whis}* because "the absence of reflexes of [Brugmann's Law](#) points to IE e-vocalism". EIEC claims that the original form was acrostatic ablauting **h₁óg^{whis}*, genitive **h₁ég^{whis}*. Whether **h₃ég^{whis}* or **h₁óg^{whis}* with a genitive **h₁ég^{whis}*, I expect that this PIE root, which likewise meant “snake; serpent”, is akin to PIE **h₂éng^{whis}* at a far-back pre-PIE stage. Also akin is PIE **h₁eǵ^{his}* “hedgehog”, because hedgehogs are known to eat snakes.

So here we have the confluence of sea and snake and eel and worm, and things that enclose, encoil, entrap, restrain; the sea was often personified/conceived of as a giant snake encircling the land, and swallowing its own tail. In Norse mythology, Loki was the father of Jörmungandr (Old Norse: *Jormungandr*, literally the Vast 'gandr': The word "gandr" can mean a variety of things in Old Norse, but mainly refers to elongated entities and or supernatural beings. Gandr can refer to, among other things: “snake, fjord, river, staff, cane, mast, penis, bind”, and the like, mainly in "supernatural" or "living" senses); Jörmungandr was also known as the Midgard Serpent or World Serpent (Old Norse: *Miðgarðsormr*), an unfathomably large sea serpent or worm who dwells in the world sea, encircling the Earth (Midgard) and biting his own tail, an example of an ouroboros. As a result of it surrounding Midgard (the Earth) it is referred to as the World Serpent. Jörmungandr releasing its tail is one of the signs of the beginning of Ragnarok (the final battle of the world).

Meanwhile, the etymon of Loki is considered to most likely be the same root that is the source of English “lock”, PIE *lewǵ, “to bend”, referring to Loki as the crooked one, the snake, the encoiler, the Sea that surrounds the earth. Loki was a crafty and cunning snake; in Albanian *ngjalë* (“eel”) also means “a crafty, cunning person”.

Loki was also very associated with the far north, the evil direction. In Latin, *aquilō* was the north wind and the north; the north was the direction not just of the colder region of the earth and sea, but also of the long polar night; and the dark storm clouds were most associated with the north.

I posit that Latin *aquilō* referred to the dark clouds and the darkness of the polar night, as well as to the engirdling North Sea and the Circumpolar Sea, from a root that meant “to enclose, to grip, to grab” (with “enclose; closed” leading to “dark”, as described earlier), likely in turn from “to bend” or from “to tighten, to make firm” (and when you bend a cord around a bundle of sticks for example, the bundle gets tight and firm).

In phrases such as “Davy Jones’ locker”, we encounter the additional idea of the sea as a locker of things that it holds in its depths; and locker connects to lock, and this word “lock” is acknowledged as the most likely cognate of Loki. And Loki was associated with crows, ravens, etc. (the dark aspect: and we have seen how “closed, locked” can shift to “dark”).

One popular theory is that the term “Baltic” in reference to the Baltic Sea derives from Latin *balteus* (“belt”), due to the shape of the sea extending around the continent like a belt. This is suggested by Adam of Bremen, who in the 11th century first recorded the name in the form *Balticus* (*Balticus, eo quod in modum baltei longo tractu per Scithicas regiones tendatur usque in Greciam*).

Some questions for a future edition: 1) is the root of Latin *aqua* and Proto-Germanic **ahwō* (and also likely the root of a Lusitanian and/or Celti-Iberian form) to be reconstructed as **h₁ek^w*- as Kilday posits (though as we see I give completely different semantics to his phonetic reconstruction) or as **h₂ek^w*-/**h₂ék^w*- as often seen in linguistic handbooks (with the full form

sometimes given as $*h_2ék^weh_2$? I have not yet spent enough time studying the evidence for which laryngeal is more likely, or whether [e] or [é] is more likely.

2) Does $*h_2ek^w-$ / $*h_2ék^w-$ / $*h_1ek^w-$ derive somehow from $*h_2ep$? Gus Kroonen is one well-known linguist who has proposed that $*h_2ek^w-$ does derive from $*h_2ep-$.

3) Or vice versa, $*h_2ep$ derives from $*h_2ek^w-$ / $*h_2ék^w-$ / $*h_1ek^w-$?

4) Or they both derive from a common ancestor?

5) Or are they chiming roots, meaning that in a sense that is hard to define they are akin, akin as regarding the initial word-formation promptings that caused them to be first expressed in such similar phonological/phonetic form, with such identical root meanings (“to curve, to bend”? “to grasp, to hold, to enclose, to engirdle” etc.) ? But they have been distinct (though akin in some sense) chiming roots since their inception before PIE?

6) Is the form $*h_2ep-$ / $*h_2eb-$ / $*h_2eb^h-$, native to PIE, but the form $*h_2ek^w-$ / $*h_2ék^w-$ / $*h_1ek^w-$ is from an ancient European Non-IE language? Can they still be considered chiming roots if one is native to PIE, and the other to Non-IE? And what if the Non-IE language in question was related to PIE?

7) I conclude, as do a number of other linguists, that Old Norse *Ægir* is cognate to Proto-Germanic $*ahwō$ and to Latin *aqua*, but I do not know exactly how: I have seen two different routes proposed: one of them² is via $*āgwi-jaz$ ('that of the river/water'), itself a derivative of the stem $*ahwō-$ ('river'; cf. Gothic *ahva* 'body of water, river', Old English *ēa* 'stream', Old High German *aha* 'river').

Another route is from the linguist Nicolás Monti's theory that *Ægir* derives from PIE $*h_2ōk^w-í-i-o$ (with an inverted breve accent mark under the second “i”, which I do not have shown), in turn from PIE $*h_2ek^w-$.

2 Haudry, 2017, pp. 29-30.

Part 2. Achilles and Achelous

I posit that Ancient Greek Ἀχιλλεύς (the form Ἀχιλλεύς is sometimes employed for metrical abbreviation in Epic), the Ancient Greek name which is the source of Achilles, derives from a reference either to the famous Shield of Achilles, the shield that was emphasized and described in great detail in the Iliad; or derives from a reference to the chariot wheel(s) of Achilles' chariot; or derives from both shield and chariot wheel(s), as well as perhaps having additional references intended, which will be discussed in the following paragraphs.

I posit this not only because of the importance of shield and chariot wheels for the character of Achilles, but also because the name of Achilles (which was/is of undetermined etymology) is so similar to Achelous (Ἀχελῷος/Ἀχελώϊος is of highly disputed etymology), a similarity which has been noted before by scholars, and that similarity, combined with some data /factors that will be discussed, make some scholars think that Achilles was once an ancient water-god/river-god/god of the sea: Achilles' mother was said to be the Nereid (sea-nymph) Thetis, a major sea-nymph and a sea-goddess. And in another tradition, as an infant Achilles was dipped into the river Styx, but he was held by one of his heels when he was dipped, and that undipped portion of him remained vulnerable.

My theory is that Ἀχελῷος/Ἀχελώϊος (which was the name of several rivers in Ancient Greece; and poetically meant “stream, water” in general; and was also used for the god who personified a given river of such name) derives from a root that referred to the bending, curving of rivers, streams and the bending/curving of the mythical giant Ocean river/stream encircling the earth; and referred also to the way rivers enclose a given region of land; and the I posit that the root-meaning also led to the meaning “wheel” /“rim of a wheel” and/or “a round shield”, such as Achilles had.

So then Achilles might not originally have been a water-god nor a river-god, and the strong association of Achilles with the northern/northwestern/northeastern part of the Black Sea and with the ends of

the earth where the round Ocean stream begins (and his association with the sea via his mother Thetis, and his association with the river Styx) has more to do with the etymology of Achilles having to do with what I described above, and not necessarily due to Achilles being exactly a river-god or water-god or ocean-god, but he came to be a demi-god hero very associated with the northern/northwestern/northeasten Black Sea, for reasons detailed here.

The wheel association also associated him with speed, and “swift-footed” is the translation of a Homeric epithet of Achilles. Rivers are often swift-running as well, as is water in a flash flood, and running water etc.

The underworld rivers Styx and the river Acheron themselves have an association with the giant Ocean river that surrounds the earth, since in many Ancient Greek and other European traditions, the Isles of the Blessed in the afterlife are located in the river Ocean, away from the lands of mortals. And the river Styx and Acheron and the river Ocean are also associated with the Milky Way in the sky, the Milky Way which is a rivers of stars which was so much thought of as the abode of souls, before birth and after death.

Achilles was thought of as residing on one of the Isles of the Blessed in the Northwestern Black Sea, specifically Achilles was thought by the Ancient Greeks to reside on Snake Island, known to the Ancient Greeks as Leuke (=“white”) island, near the coasts of Romania and Ukraine.

The fabled Race-course of Achilles is a sandbar in the sea located off the central northern coast of the Black Sea off the coast of Crimea, Ukraine.

This Ancient Greek Ἀχ- found in Achilles and Achelous I expect is cognate to the Ἀχ- in Ἀχέρων (Acheron, a river in Greece and a river in the underworld), which itself is most likely (in my opinion, despite Beekes’ conclusion) cognate to Proto-Balto-Slavic *éžera , “lake” and Old Armenian եզր (ezr) which has the meanings “edge, shore, limit, end”. Additional cognates include Kamkata-vari azo/aziu=“pond”; Waigali aza (“pond”); Kamakata-vari and Waigali are Indo-Iranian languages, and these words are already thought to be cognates to the Armenian and Balto-Slavic words.

Further cognates are Proto-Balto-Slavic **eža-* “weir; balk; boundary strip”.

The root-word likely had the form **h₁éǵʰ-*, and was cognate with PIE **h₁éǵʰis* “snake”, both from “to curve, bend”/“to encircle, encircle, to hold, restrain, to grasp”. PIE **h₁éǵʰis* “snake” is the source of Ancient Greek ἔχιδνα (“snake, adder, viper”), rendered ekhis/echis in the Roman alphabet, similar to Achilles/Achilles, who was said to reside on Snake Island in the Black Sea (known in Romanian as Marea Neagră, with Marea=sea and Neagră =black) off the coast of Romania and Ukraine.

Part 3. A stroll down to the sea, La Mer/Marea

I find it quite interesting that we find PIE **móri* (“sea; standing water”) and PIE **mer* “sea, lake, wetland”, and Sumerian mir-du-na “belt” and Sumerian mir (“north wind, north, storm”) and Sumerian Mir meaning “snake; and a mythical giant serpent that encircles the earth; the Ocean river” and Sumerian mar meaning “worm”;

And in Persian mar=snake, dragon.

In Ancient Greek *μέρμνος* and *μέρμνης* are of unknown etymology and the words referred to a type of hawk (and hawks are known to fly in circles, besides the fact that they grab/enclose their prey with their taloned-toes, and they have hook-like curved beaks and talons). And in Ancient Greek *μόρφνος* / *μορφνός* referred to a kind of eagle. And in Ancient Greek *μοριφόν* was a word for “dark”, and see also Ancient Greek *μόρον* = “black mulberry; blackberry”.

I posit that Ancient Greek *μορφή* (which means “shape, form, outline” etc.)---which was of undetermined etymology before this paper---derives from “that which holds”, as an outline holds what is inside, for example the outline of a shape, a form.

And “mara” was a rarely used Ancient Greek word for “hand” according to an Ancient Greek gloss.

More details and additional information coming in the next edition

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